

Comparative Study on Current and Future Business Process

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Abstract:

In the current generation, the AI tool is the most important and common tool in the various fields especially in the business, education etc. This paper defines the AI tool use in the business. AI is the fundamental component of the business process. AI tool is reducing the cost of use and development of human task in the business, where AI is providing automation of work to reduce the human difficulties. AI will continue to evolution for the future enhancement in the business to shift towards the success.

Keywords: *Artificial Intelligence, Business Intelligence, future of AI in Business.*

I. Introduction:

Artificial intelligence in short term AI is the branch of electronics and computer science; the machine or computer system will be able to learn and make the decision making. AI is the simulation of the Human. Business uses the AI for improve the performance such as setting, rule engines, and search engine. AI helps business operations by showing the flow of work-data and decision making. AI helps in automating tasks and provides personalized experiences from employees and consumer by collecting the valuable data. AI increases the capabilities of business software such as amazon, Flipkart etc.

AI is raising the Business by investment profits and technology in the organization. According to the recent report, the global AI service market consist of AI software tools and services, the growth of the business in 2024 is \$12.88 billion.

II. General Risks of Business and Solution suing AI:

- 1. Decision-making Power:** In real-time, the business must be able to function fast, accurately and flexible according to the business condition. According to the Survey, the improvement of business is based on Decision making of business conditions. When the Decision making is Manual there will be inaccurate results, it cannot be rapid, flexible due to this, the business progress will be decreased. With the help of AI technology, the employees in the business can generate accurate data along with predictions based on right decisions. But even if an AI system provides the employee super intelligence power, it does not be accurate and not timely decision that means it may consume more time to decide or the decision will not be satisfy. Hence, there is need of proper judgment in the business by using AI tool in decision making power.

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- 2. Competitive Advantage:** Business in the market as high-level of competition. AI tool used in the business to have greater potential to improve the business operations for longer periods. AI will adopt the best data and well-trained software to set the business competition.

AI will adopt 65% of competitive advantages in the business. Hence, AI in Business will explore the many competitive advantages to push forward to develop and marketing.

- 3. Business Insights and Revenue Growth:** AI tool offers a variety of ways in business to increase the data volumes; it provides the capabilities for data mining for some business relevant. AI collects and analyzes the data for more powerful. AI effort to gain the marketing shares and also expand services and products.

III. Implementation of AI in the Business:

Implementation of AI in the Business is done in 3 simple steps:

Step1: Identify the problem: It is the Initial step in the implementation. It finds the inefficient areas in the business to be process and examine how the AI can potentially handle it.

Step2: Collect data: The AI will collect the Business data and analyze. Then process the document based on analyzed data and creates a valuable report

Step3: Train the AI model: The AI output will based on the input; hence the entering input should be very accurate to get accurate output. Relevant documents will be a output that provides the business process and valuable AI automation will be proved.

IV. Main challenges of AI in the Business:

- 1. Bias in AI:** AI is trained in business to recognize the step-wise process to give the solutions for Business.
- 2. Data Privacy and Security:** Every Business should take the security in all the operations. The Important Business data should be confidential. The data should be protected from company and customer considered as bad actor.
- 3. Shortage of AI Professionals:** It focus on the AI Professional Technology to keep the track of achievement of specific business goals, with compliance and security and improve the role in optimizing the technology.

V. AI use cases in Business:

- 1. Manufacturing:** AI helps continuous learning, recognize activity and prevent the fraudulent transactions. It use the automating Fraud prevention in the business to provide best customer service.
- 2. High Speed:** AI helps in the optimization of business for current and future. The business processing speed will be very fast without depending on human interaction.

3. Financial services: AI will provide the best profit in the business.

VI. Future enhancement of AI in Business:

AI in the business holds the future efficiency

1. Development and Adoption of Generative AI will accelerate:

AI can improve the business in next decades. AI continues to evolution of business by extending the basic tasks to complex tasks solving and also helps in development of new products or services.

2. Collaboration between humans and AI:

AI cannot completely replace the human interaction. To make successful business the AI and human can work together.

3. Ethical considerations:

AI use is more prevalent in the business to have larger focus on responsible. It ensures the fair and transparent decision-making processes.

VII. Conclusion:

AI technology is effective tool of business in the current period and also it is helpful in the future enhancement. AI is the important development tool in the business, it offers many number of opportunities for business innovation and efficiency. Apply from customer services to operational optimization in the transformative potential. AI will navigate the business complexity; it is balancing the business between technological advancement and ethical responsibility. AI will ensure the data privacy, positive changes and successful integration in the business. AI business will provide collaborative approach in both technology power and human values.

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